

Towards Designing Circular Systemic Solutions: A User-Centric Approach

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Abstract—Circular Systemic Solutions (CSSs) can enable circular economy transitions with the assistance of value chains, stakeholders’ collaboration, and digital support tools. However, the alignment of digital capabilities with the stakeholder needs from different domains and regions is challenging. This paper utilizes a user-centric approach to link the design of CSS cyber-physical systems with stakeholder user-centred requirements. The use of surveys and workshops in four different regional CSS use cases (Greece, Italy, Germany, Portugal) and one interregional case, extracted 1171 user-centred requirements, which were then consolidated through a three-cycle merging process, into 45 high-level requirements grouped into six categories. A dual-lens analysis was performed that combines the share of merged inputs per category with structural priority to identify the most recurring needs from foundational system necessities. The results emphasize the need for stakeholder engagement and collaboration, knowledge management with transparency, and monitoring and visualization. The findings support the design of a modular cyber-physical system integrating a digital platform that remains adaptable, reusable, and aligned with the evolving stakeholder needs in circular value chains.

Keywords—circular economy, circular systemic solution, user-centred requirements, requirements engineering, stakeholder engagement, cyber-physical systems, decision support

I. INTRODUCTION

Circular Economy (CE) is emerging as a solution to transition from linear production and consumption models toward resource efficiency, waste reduction, and regenerative value chains. Often this transition is fostered and enabled by the integration of digital technologies, such as data platforms, cyber-physical systems, and decision-support tools to improve traceability, monitoring, and coordination in different complex value networks. Within this context, CSSs form the

basis in accelerating circular economy transitions with the implementation of resource reuse through integrated value chains, stakeholder collaboration and the use of digital tools [1], [2]. However, CSS implementation is complex because it requires the alignment of different actors, infrastructures, regulatory constraints, and market information across the multiple circular value chains [3], [4], [5].

Although technological options to support circular transitions exist, it is difficult to align tools with stakeholders’ needs and objectives, and regional constraints [3], [4]. A CSS is a socio-technical system whose effectiveness depends on the adoption, trust, and coordination of its stakeholders beyond the digital solutions that may support it; therefore, the design of a CSS supporting system should be tailored to stakeholder needs [6], [7]. A user-centric design based on the integration of surveys, workshops, and co-creation sessions, can identify stakeholder needs and assist designers to define requirements that reflect practical constraints and expectations, including traceability, transparency, monitoring of key performance indicators, regulatory compliance, and decision support for resource and logistics [8], [9], [10].

This paper presents the operationalization of a user-centric approach to support circular systemic transitions by linking CSS value chain conceptualization with stakeholder-driven requirements extraction, as well as aligning those requirements with digital solution capabilities. It includes a structured multi-cycle merging process that consolidates 1171 extracted user-centred requirements and a dual-lens analysis that combines share of merged requirements with structural priority to assist in the design of a cyber-physical system that integrates a digital platform that designs and operates CSSs.

The remainder of this paper is structured as follows. Section 2 investigates related work on requirement

mechanisms approaches in circular and systemic contexts and presents the main challenges identified in circular systemic transitions. Section 3 presents the methodology that was used to extract the user-centred requirements, including the engagement activities of the stakeholders, the data collection process, and multi-stage merging approach for the requirements extraction. Section 4 analyzes the final set of high-level user-centred requirements, identifies the most mentioned themes and discusses their implications in the design of digital support solutions, as well as their potential for reuse across different domains. Finally, section 5 concludes the paper and outlines possible future directions.

II. RELATED WORK

The design and implementation of CE and CSSs depend on structured requirement approaches to manage the complexity across value chains, stakeholder groups, and lifecycle stages [3], [5]. Existing methodologies highlight the importance of addressing technical, environmental, economic, and social challenges in the definition of system requirements, most importantly in implementations where multiple actors and interdependent processes must be aligned [6], [11]. Several approaches focus on the definition of requirements based on value chain analysis, lifecycle assessment, and sustainability assessment frameworks (e.g., value chain modeling, life cycle assessment, sustainability indicators) [12], [13], [14]. Although these technologies support the identification of functional and non-functional requirements that relate to resource efficiency, traceability, performance monitoring, and regulatory compliance, they often focus on analytical or assessment-driven perspectives and provide limited focus to stakeholder feedback and end-user validation throughout the design process.

Many studies highlight systemic and participatory approaches, where the requirements are defined based on stakeholder activities, such as workshops, surveys, and co-creation sessions. These studies argue that requirements in circular systems cannot be fully predefined and should be able to be updated and enhanced as the system evolves and additional challenges are identified [8], [15], [16].

At the same time, the transition toward a real-world circular systemic solution is a dynamic and evolving process that requires the establishment of collaborative multi-actor ecosystems characterized by interdependencies, trust, and coordination challenges [17], [18], [19]. Therefore, to achieve the common goals, all stakeholders should have meaningful engagements, shared purpose, and structured communication across value chains [20], [21], while digital tools and solutions should bridge gaps across the multidisciplinary networks of stakeholders, and remain aligned with stakeholder needs, as well as ensure adaptability to real operational contexts [22], [23].

Nevertheless, a gap remains in the structured methodologies that consistently combine and integrate user-centred requirements into the design of digital tools and operational system architectures in CSS contexts. This paper addresses this gap with the operationalization of a user-centric methodology that links stakeholder user-centred requirement extraction with digital system design and cyber-physical architecture alignment.

III. METHODOLOGY FOR EXTRACTING USER-CENTRED REQUIREMENTS

A. Circular Systemic Solutions and Domains Addressed

The design and full implementation of CSSs at the regional and local scales are complex due to the involvement of multidisciplinary stakeholders and actors, who share a common vision but distinct points of view. For this reason, a tailor-made methodology is required to guide all stakeholders and actors, including local decision-makers, policy makers, public authorities, private companies, research institutions and citizens [24]. Such a methodology should reflect the needs of stakeholders and their interdependencies among them. The deployment of CSS in cities and regions cannot be the responsibility of a single stakeholder or actor, but rather of an ecosystem [25]. In this context, digital advancements emerge as efficient solutions for sharing information, resources and knowledge, building trustful and transparent ecosystems [26].

Such ecosystems have been developed in CSS use cases to assist in the extraction of user-centred requirements. More specifically, four multi-disciplinary and regional CSS use cases were analyzed, including agriculture and by-product valorization (Greece), wastewater reuse and nutrient recovery (Italy), plastic waste recycling (Germany), and circular public transport systems (Portugal), alongside an interregional multi-national CSS use case that combines the key value chains from the rest regional CSS use cases to investigate methods to maximize circularity and identify growth opportunities.

Building on the requirements of stakeholders in these domains, a harmonized methodology is developed to address their multidisciplinary aspects and needs, creating value for all of them derived from new CSS products and services [27], [28].

B. Survey Design, Workshops, and Stakeholder Groups

A stepwise approach was followed for the extraction and definition of the user-centred requirements as presented in Fig. 1. The process was initiated with the conduction of individual interviews with the key stakeholders, such as primary resource providers, manufacturers, distributors, researchers, and end-users, aimed at gathering initial insights regarding their priorities, needs, and the challenges they faced. The inputs from the interviews were then analyzed to identify the common themes and shared concerns. This analysis was then used as the basis for the design of a structured survey aimed at enabling the systematic collection and validation of stakeholder perspectives, as well as enabling the extraction of user-centred requirements.

The structured survey was distributed among domain experts to ensure that all questions necessary to yield important requirements were included. The feedback received was analyzed to refine the content of the survey and ensure alignment with the stakeholder's expectations. Following the refinement, the survey was disseminated to stakeholders to collect and analyze their feedback. Subsequently, workshops with stakeholders were organized to validate and discuss the survey analysis results, ensuring the reliability and completeness of the survey findings, as well as to collect any additional insights that may not have been captured through the survey.

The validated workshop insights and the survey results assisted in the definition of the circular value chains. Subsequently, the survey results and defined value chains

were analyzed to extract the user-centered requirements. This approach provided a consolidated representation of stakeholder needs and formed the foundation for subsequent digital solution selection.

Fig. 1. User-centred requirements extraction approach

C. Data Collection and Initial Processing

The data collection process was designed to extract qualitative and quantitative information that relates to stakeholder needs, operational practices, and systemic challenges of the included CSS value chains. The survey addressed different categories, including Domain needs and systemic challenges; Social, technical, economic, and regulatory barriers; Stakeholder engagement and support structures; Knowledge levels, awareness, and past circular initiatives; Urban metabolism data (e.g., material flows, water, energy, food, emissions); Decision-making and risk management practices; Supply chain mapping and actor roles; Circular processes, KPIs, and monitoring approaches; Existing and desired technological solutions; Strategic goals, expected outcomes, and stakeholder motivations; and Policy alignment and institutional context; Stakeholder typologies and co-creation roles.

The survey responses were reviewed to ensure that they were completed and consistent before the analysis. The qualitative inputs were processed and grouped together based on their theme, while the quantitative responses were combined to enable comparisons between different stakeholders and domains. This step ensured that the collected data could be systematically analyzed and used in the requirement extraction process that would follow.

D. Context-Based and Quantitative Analysis for Requirements Extraction

The combination of survey results and the defined value chains assisted in the extraction of 1171 user-centered requirements. The extraction grouping process was conducted in 3 merging cycles, each with a specific objective, as illustrated in Fig. 2.

In the first merging cycle, the requirements were subsequently investigated and refined to remove the duplicates. This process resulted in a reduced set of 952 user-centred requirements.

In the second merging cycle, the remaining requirements were grouped based on their context and merged. Those referred to the requirements that addressed the same functionalities, stakeholder objectives, or systemic challenges. For example, the requirements “The system shall educate end-users on sustainability benefits to drive demand for circular

Fig. 2. Merging cycles of the extraction process

products” and “The system shall address resistance to change stemming from traditional economic models” were merged to produce the “The system shall enhance stakeholder understanding and improve social acceptance of circular economy practices.” user-centred requirement. This process resulted in a refined set of 356 user-centered requirements.

In the final merging cycle, the requirements were further grouped to achieve higher-level abstraction and harmonization. The overlapping requirements were further grouped based on shared underlying needs, common decision-support objectives, and recurring cross-domain patterns. This process focused on the alignment of requirements from different CSS domains and stakeholder groups, ensuring consistency in scope and interpretation, while maintaining user intent. For example, as illustrated in Fig. 3, three requirements that relate to stakeholder collaboration were merged into one requirement. As a result, all the requirements were merged into a final set of 45 high-level user-centered requirements.

IV. ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION OF FINAL USER-CENTRED REQUIREMENTS

A. Analytical Framework for Requirement Evaluation

As described in the previous section, the extraction and merging cycles process resulted in the final set of 45 high-level user-centred requirements. These requirements were consolidated into six overarching categories reflecting the stakeholder needs across domains.

Their evaluation included the merging intensity, measured as the number of merged requirements for each category and expressed as a share of the total merged inputs, and the structural prioritization measured through a MoSCoW-based theme [29]. The prioritization levels were defined based on how frequently each merged requirement reoccurred in the stakeholders’ inputs that were collected from the survey and

workshop, considering their relevance to the system’s objectives.

In addition, to maintain the traceability between the high-level requirements and the context under which they were extracted, each user-centred requirement includes a description for its use case related class. This descriptor includes information regarding the region (regional operational context), CSS type (e.g., agriculture, livestock/food, wastewater, plastics, vehicles, or all), and stakeholder class (e.g., supply chain operator, manufacturers, policy makers, consumers). It supports cross-domain

Fig. 3. Final merging cycle example

reusability, where requirements don’t relate to a single domain, but can be associated with classes of circular value chains and stakeholder ecosystems to enable their replication and adaptation in different contexts.

Table 1 presents the distribution of mandatory and desirable requirements in each category, along with the share of total merged requirements.

B. Merging Intensity Across Categories

Based on the share of total merged requirements, stakeholders mostly mentioned requirements that relate to Stakeholder Engagement, Collaboration, and Market Enablement. They emphasize the importance of the social layer in circular transitions, as well as supply chain visibility and waste valorization for operational transparency and resource recovery.

Information and knowledge sharing, management, and transparency was also category with many mentioned requirements, which reflects the demand for a unified, trustworthy knowledge system that integrates models and decision-support mechanisms. Stakeholders emphasized the need to have access to consistent, credible, interpretable information for resource flows, operational constraints, and system performance across value chains.

C. Structural Criticality and Priority Distribution

From a structural perspective, requirements that relate to stakeholder engagement contain the most mandatory requirements, which indicates the need for systems that include feedback collection, co-creation, knowledge exchange, and reuse of already established CSSs, to support learning, trust, and long-term adoptions from different stakeholders.

CSS value chain monitoring, KPIs, and visualization requirements were also set as mandatory, indicating that many

stakeholders expressed the need for continuous visibility, such as KPIs, flow, and compliance, and integrated feedback mechanisms. Stakeholders require real-time or near real-time insights to support them in making operational and strategic decisions.

Table 1. User-centred requirements categories priority distribution

Category	# Mandatory	# Desirable	Share of total merged requirements
Stakeholder Engagement, Collaboration, and Market Enablement	3	8	28%
Information and Knowledge Sharing, Management, and Transparency	1	4	17.6%
CSS Value Chain Analytics, Simulation, and Decision Support	1	10	15.1%
CSS Value Chain Monitoring, KPIs, and Visualization	2	2	14.5%
CSS Risk, Compliance, and Quality	1	6	13.2%
Circular Processes and Resource Valorization	1	6	11.6%

In contrast, analytics and simulation related requirements, although they have strong merging intensity, they don’t contain many mandatory requirements, which indicates that their role in system capabilities could be used as enabling rather than foundational.

D. Thematic Interpretation of Requirement Categories

Information and Knowledge Sharing, Management, and Transparency requirements relate to the integration of data systems, search, information discovery, credibility, and resource quality. An example of this category includes the need for integrated data, modeling, and decision-support tools that can track resource flows, environmental quality, and operational performance while enhancing logistics efficiency, inventory management, and supply chain coordination within circular economy simulations. The use case related classes of most requirements in this category include stakeholders, such as supply chain operators, policymakers, or manufacturers, and all available CSS types.

CSS Value Chain Monitoring, KPIs, and Visualization requirements relate to dashboards, multi-level KPIs, benchmarking, supply-chain visibility, and visual analytics. An example of this category is the requirement for monitoring systems, interactive dashboards, KPI tracking tools, and environmental impact assessments across different aggregation levels (industry, CE stream, CSS, value chain, region/market) to provide actionable insights into logistics, resource flows and utilization, compliance, and sustainability performance, facilitating information exchange. The use case related classes of most requirements in this category include stakeholders, such as industry or logistic providers, and all available CSS types.

Stakeholder Engagement, Collaboration, and Market Enablement requirements that relate to feedback loops, collaboration platforms, awareness/training, partnerships, funding, scaling, competitiveness, and barrier reduction. An example of this category is the need for digital platforms and

collaborative frameworks to facilitate stakeholder collaboration, best practice exchange, decision support, and supply chain coordination to enhance efficiency in circular economy initiatives. The use case related classes of most requirements in this category include stakeholders, such as product manufacturers or businesses, and regional operational contexts.

CSS Value Chain Analytics, Simulation, and Decision Support requirements relate to AI tools, logistic/storage/procurement optimization, recommendations, and inefficiency detection. An example of this category is the need for digital tools to support stakeholders in assessing and improving the efficiency of distribution processes within circular supply chains. The use case related classes of most requirements in this category include stakeholders, such as businesses or investors, and all available CSS types.

CSS Risk, Compliance, and Quality requirements that relate to risk analytics, regulatory adherence, lifecycle assessments for compliance, quality management, and certifications. An example of this category is the need for predictive analytics and digital risk assessment tools to support stakeholders in identifying and mitigating risks (e.g., high transitioning costs limited end-user awareness), enhancing operational efficiency, and ensuring compliance within circular economy supply chains. The use case related classes of most requirements in this category include stakeholders, such as businesses or industry, and all available CSS types.

Circular Processes and Resource Valorization requirements relate to waste-to-value strategies, safe resource and materials reuse, and best-practice protocols. An example of this category is the need for digital tools and decision-support systems to optimize waste valorization, while ensuring regulatory compliance and environmental sustainability across circular supply chains. The use case related classes of most requirements in this category include stakeholders, such as waste processors or manufacturers, and all available CSS types.

E. Implications for Systemic Design in Circular Transitions

The findings revealed that circular transitions need systemic design approaches that can address various technical, social, economic, and regulatory challenges.

Regarding the technical barriers, issues such as lack of tools that monitor material quality, isolated infrastructures, lack of traceability, and limitations in processing technologies highlight the need for integrated, interoperable systems that are reliable and scalable. Therefore, cyber-physical system designs should integrate real-time data acquisition, standardized data exchange mechanisms, and traceability functionalities that connect physical resource flows in different value chains. This integration can reduce isolation, improve transparency, and enable coordination between different infrastructures.

Social challenges include resistance to change, limited awareness, and trust deficits among the different stakeholders, highlighting the importance of enabling engagement, communication, and training mechanisms into circular economy systems. This suggests that cyber-physical systems should enable participation and collaboration functionalities, including feedback loops, role-based access, KPI

visualization, and knowledge sharing environments that can enhance trust and maintain stakeholder engagement.

Furthermore, economic and market challenges, such as high upfront investment costs, competition with lower-cost conventional alternatives, and unstable market demand, highlight the need for financial innovation and supportive policy frameworks. Moreover, regulatory gaps and non-unified standards limit circular adoption, which suggests that system design should be aligned with regulatory frameworks and evolving policy requirements.

Overall, these findings suggest that systemic design in circular transitions should not only focus on technical optimization, but also integrate social acceptance, economic viability, and governance alignment into digital solutions to ensure resilience, adoption, and long-term sustainability of circular value chains. Therefore, cyber-physical systems should integrate analytics and compliance monitoring functionalities to enable stakeholders to assess economic viability, calculate impacts, evaluate risks, and ensure regulatory compliance prior to the implementation of operational changes. The integration of these functionalities can support decision-making and reduce uncertainty in circular transitions.

F. Potential for Reuse in Other Domains or CSS Solutions

The requirement analysis indicates that stakeholder requirements overlap across domains. Regardless of the differences in materials, processes, and regulatory contexts, they generally prioritize visibility, coordination, assurance, and knowledge exchange. This overlap enables the potential of reusing requirement structures and design concepts in different circular domains, considering the systems are developed with customizable capabilities rather than fixed implementations.

The use of priority levels on the user-centred requirements, based on how frequently they were mentioned by the stakeholders, further enhances the development of an incremental and adaptive system, which allows foundational functionalities to be implemented first. Furthermore, it enables progressive enhancement as the systems mature. Additionally, the assignment of use case related classes (region, domain type, stakeholder role) in the requirements, enables transferability and supports replication and scaling of circular solutions in different regions.

Therefore, digital support for circular systemic transitions should be viewed as modular, user-centred ecosystems that integrate information management, decision support, assessment, and collaboration functionalities. Designing the system based on stakeholder extracted requirements can reduce the gap between conceptual circular strategies and realistically implementable solutions, while supporting adoption, adaptability, and sustainability.

V. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

This paper presented a structured, user-centric approach to support circular systemic transitions through the systematic extraction, consolidation, and analysis of user-centred requirements related to CSS design and operationalization, as these were defined by relevant stakeholders. The final set of high-level user-centred requirements revealed common themes across domains and stakeholders, relating to transparency, monitoring, decision support, risk management, and stakeholder collaboration.

These findings emphasize the socio-technical nature of circular systemic transitions and the importance of designing digital support solutions that include information management, analytics, assurance, and engagement functionalities. The paper prioritized the requirements based on frequency of occurrence, which enabled the identification of shared and recurring needs in different domains, while it also supported a structured alignment between the stakeholder expectations and the cyber-physical system capabilities.

Future work includes the refinement of the presented approach through iterative validation and its integration within holistic application frameworks for the design and operationalization of CSSs. This includes the enhanced integration of user-centred requirements into a cyber-physical system's design decisions, and exploration on the support of different circular domains and regional contexts with modular and configurable digital capabilities. Additionally, emphasis will be given on the validation of requirement prioritization over time, as stakeholder needs evolve and the developed circular systems mature.

Additional research may include the investigation of feedback loops and performance monitoring mechanisms and their utilization on continuously updating the requirements and system configurations to support long-term adaptability and governance alignment. Overall, the presented approach presents a foundation for developing scalable, reusable, and user-centred digital support structures that can integrate the design, adoption, and sustainability of CSSs in different contexts.

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